
MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM AS A COMPLEMENTARY THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PROSTATE CANCER

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ABSTRACT

Integrative and Complementary Health Practices (IChP) became a Brazilian National Policy in 2006 in accordance with Traditional, Complementary and Integrative Medicine (TCIM), used by the World Health Organization (WHO). Although not part of IChP, Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is an integrative and complementary practice that uses Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) generated by therapeutic magnets that are applied externally to the body on Biomagnetic Pairs (BMPs), causing depolarization and regulate the pH balance in the impacted region, leading the organism to homeostasis. Considering that Prostatic Adenocarcinoma is the second cause of mortality among men, the objective of this study is to present a protocol for the application of the MB technique for the treatment of tumoral phenomena. This research presents results of an integrative literature review. For the collection and selection of articles, the bibliographic databases PubMed, SciELO, BVS and Google Scholar

were used. Having as a limiting factor the few studies involving the MB, understanding these aspects is essential not only for the authors of this type of research but also to expand knowledge in all areas of health promotion.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Static Magnetic Field; Magnetotherapy; Prostatic Adenocarcinoma; Traditional Complementary and Integrative Medicines (TCIM); Integrative and Complementary Practices in Health (ICPH); Complementary and Integrative Therapy.

INTRODUCTION

The Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) was organized in 1902 and serves as the regional office of the World Health Organization (WHO) for the Americas in order to improve the health and quality of life of their population. According to the Pan-American Health Organization (PAHO), Traditional, Complementary and Integrative Medicine (TCIM) constitute an important model of health care, being in many countries the main offer of services. (MINISTÉRIO SAÚDE, 2021).

The Brazilian Ministry of Health, through Ordinance No. 971/2006, published the National Policy on Integrative and Complementary Practices (PICS) in the Unified Health System (SUS). The PICS are the health practices carried out by health professionals based on the model of humanized care and centered on the integrality of the individual. The PICS seek to stimulate the natural mechanisms for preventing injuries, promoting and recovering health through effective and safe technologies, with an emphasis on welcoming listening, the development of a therapeutic bond and the integration of human beings with the environment and society (PAHO, 2022).

The importance of this National Policy is highlighted, therefore, cancer, a term that encompasses different types of malignant diseases and that has in common the uncontrolled growth of cells that can invade adjacent tissues or organs at a distance that determines the formation of tumors, as the cells divide rapidly and can become aggressive and uncontrollable, spreading to other regions of the body (INCA, 2020).

PROSTATE ADENOCARCINOMA (PROSTATE CANCER)

According to data from the National Cancer Institute (INCA), there are an estimated 65,840 new cases of prostate cancer each year, which corresponds to a risk of 62.95 new cases per 100,000 men. Despite therapeutic advances, about 25% of patients with prostate cancer still die from the disease and 20% are still diagnosed in advanced stages (SBU, 2022).

The choice of the type of treatment for Prostate Cancer (PCa), the most common of which is Prostatic Adenocarcinoma, is based on the stage of the disease and the most suitable methods of existing treatment. These include vigilant observation in special situations, hormone therapy, surgeries, radiotherapy and specific drug treatment that have temporary or permanent undesirable side effects (INCA, 2022).

The main predisposing factors that increase the individual's risk of being affected by Prostate Cancer are age over 65 years, African descent, genetic predisposition, exposure to ultraviolet radiation, smoking, alcoholism, having already undergone vasectomy surgery and having a rich diet with plenty of animal fat; red meat, calcium and milk (BRAVO *et al.*, 2022). More than 90% of prostate cancers are represented by adenocarcinomas. Hyperplasia is benign and evolves slowly and progressively. The sudden appearance of urinary difficulty in an individual with a satisfactory voiding pattern can be a sign of the manifestation of malignant disease (GABRIOTTI *et al.*, 2011).

STATIC MAGNETIC FIELDS – SMF

Our nervous system acts through electrical impulses, and the organism is capable of restoring and readjusting malfunctioning aspects. The ions present inside the neuron produce an electric current when it depolarizes. Abnormal impulses reach the brain, which processes them and sends a signal in response. Along the path, abnormal impulses can be rectified by applying appropriate electrical currents through magnetic fields (BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

According to Markov (2014), the development of Natural Sciences provides evidence that primitive cells originated in the presence of various factors, such as magnetic and electromagnetic fields. SMF have been used for the treatment of injuries with the aim of treating inflammation and pain in a non-invasive, safe and easy-to-apply way.

The human body produces magnetic fields called Biomagnetic fields, detectable in various parts of the body, including the brain, liver and heart (CARNEIRO *et al.*, 2000).

In general, the information on the characteristics of the poles of the magnets and their correlation with the positive and negative charges of the biochemical elements are relevant because they act concomitantly in the therapeutic system of Medicinal Biomagnetism, in the reestablishment of the bioelectric balance, influencing the homeostasis of the organism (GOIZ DURAN, 2008).

MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM – MB

The Dr. Albert Roy Davis and Walter C. Rawls JR (1982) have already measured the effects of magnet therapy on living beings. Using magnetic energy, they produced tissue restoration and neutralized many symptoms. In one of the findings, they observed cancer reversal reaching a rate of 90% in the treatment of rodent skin.

Broeringmeyer (1991) found that different organs of the human body have fluctuating magnetic fields due to bodily chemical activities. As such, all cells in the living organism have a specific magnetic value, and as a result, all living beings are “magnetic electric beings” controlled by means of electromagnetic energy fields.

Mexican scientist, physiotherapist and physician Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán developed a therapeutic technique called Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) at the end of the 1980s. MB is a complete therapeutic system capable of encompassing the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of Biomagnetic Couples (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008). Therapy developed by Dr. Goiz is one of the ways to use SMF. His

technique uses magnets in pairs, is non-invasive, inexpensive and has almost no restrictions.

According with the Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán (2008), pathological and pathogenic manifestations are formed from two poles, a north pole that maintains the negative charges of biochemical elements, such as OH⁻ (alkaline), and the south pole that maintains positive charges of biochemical elements, such as H⁺ (acidity). By applying the magnetic field of the north pole of a magnet, there is a sedation effect on impacted sites that present hyper alkalinity, promoting a decrease in painful stimuli.

For this to happen, the magnetic fields must be at least 1,000 Gauss in power or 0.1 Tesla. The common goal of both Broeringmeyer and Durán was to obtain a state of normality in the body called Normal Energy Level (NEL) (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

The identification of Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP) obeys the energetic resonance of the pole of the magnet with the dysfunctional polarity of the organism. It starts with the north pole (-) of a magnet, called a tracker, moving it around the regions of the body in order to identify the dysfunctions that tend to alkalinity. In places where there is a change in polarity, the phenomenon of shortening of the right hemibody occurs, which is corrected in the impaction of the resonant point with the south pole (+) of another magnet. The BMP is impacted, depolarizing it and enabling the homeostasis of the regions. According to the theory of Dr. Goiz, the vibratory and energetic resonance between two biomagnetic points of opposite polarity is related to the symbiosis of microorganisms. MB is a complete therapeutic system capable of encompassing bioelectric diagnosis, treatment of BMPs and disease prevention (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, 2021).

Therefore, it is emphasized that this work is of paramount importance, and without the intention of exhausting the subject, to present the MB, as a complementary therapy to the treatment of patients with Prostatic Adenocarcinoma. Its objective is to analyze in the researched literature, based on the theoretical framework, the possibility of applicability of a protocol for the

treatment of people with Prostatic Adenocarcinoma. And also, to provoke new designs of studies in this sphere as a complementary and integrative therapy of great value for the treatment of tumoral phenomena.

METHODOLOGY

The methodological design of this research was structured from an integrative literature review, based on six proposals in the preparation of the review by Whitemore and Kanaf (2005), according to researchers from the Ribeirão Preto School of Nursing (RUELA *et al.*, 2018).

This modality allows the synthesis of multiple studies, enables general conclusions and consists of identifying the theme, selection of the hypothesis or research question; establishment of inclusion and exclusion criteria, sampling or literature search; definition of information to be extracted from selected studies, categorization of studies; evaluation of the studies that were included; interpretation of results; presentation of the review, synthesis of knowledge (RUELA *et al.*, 2018).

The guiding question of this integrative review is the presentation of a protocol with BMPs in clinical cases of patients with Prostatic Adenocarcinoma as complementary therapy.

In the bibliographic survey stage, articles were gathered on the following platforms: Brazil Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciElo Brasil); US National Library of Medicine (PubMed); Virtual Health Library (VHL) and Google Scholar. Books for the theoretical framework are available in the virtual library of the postgraduate course at Instituto Par Magnético (BOSSA, 2021).

The following descriptors were used: Medical Biomagnetism, Biomagnetic Pair, Static Magnetic Field, Magnetotherapy, Prostate Adenocarcinoma, Complementary and Integrative Therapy, Integrative and Complementary Practices in Health, together with Boolean operators: AND and or OR.

The research began in February and ended in July 2022. Articles on the academic platforms described above were selected without restriction of chronological time, and articles published in Portuguese, Spanish and English were accepted.

The selection of articles considered the following inclusion criteria: a) Prostate cancer, specifically Prostatic Adenocarcinoma; b) Medicinal Biomagnetism therapy; c) empirical, experimental and clinical research; d) systematic research study with meta-analysis; e) relevant books and handouts on the theoretical concept of Medicinal Biomagnetism.

The exclusion criteria of the articles obeyed the following variables: a) not meeting the theme; b) not answering the guiding question; c) unavailability of access to the full text of the article online and free of charge; d) not being the result of quantitative research and integrative review; e) not being in Portuguese, English or Spanish.

First, the articles were selected by reading the title and abstract, according to the guiding question and the eligibility criteria as shown in Figure 1.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Article Selection Flowchart

Source: The Authors (2022).

Chart 1: Selected studies on Proposed Medicinal Biomagnetism Protocol as Complementary Therapy in the treatment of Prostate Cancer..

Authors	Method	Goal	Participants	Result	Conclusion
PEREZ, 2022	NIH3T3 Fibroblast Cell Culture	Addressing the effects of exposure to external static magnetic fields of different directions and magnitudes on fibroblasts in culture.	Fibroblast cells NIH3T3, in cell culture medium DMEM-F12	Significant effects of exposure to static magnetic fields were identified only on cell proliferation and mitosis rate, however, before the magnetic field the cells did not modify the migration speed	In this work we identified significant effects of exposure to magnetic fields under the conditions experienced only on cell proliferation and mitosis rate in 3T3 fibroblasts
Medeiros <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Developed support for culture plates with magnets	Evaluate the effects of magnetic stimulation on different cell lines	Cell culture of the Neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y lineage	Exposure of SMS from SH-SY5Y cells led to a decrease in cell viability, there was a decrease in apoptotic cells associated with an increase in the number of necrotic cells, a potentially safe technique in the protocol used (0.3T SMS/24h)	Considering the parameters of this research, SMS is a tool with potential for the treatment of neural tumors.
Damyanov <i>et al.</i> (2019a)	Application of the Medicinal Biomagnetism technique in conjunction with Insulin Potentiated Therapy (IPT) in patients with advanced metastatic tumors.	Improving the condition of the patient when faced with a diagnosis of tumor phenomena	10 cases of advanced metastatic cancers	The study demonstrated complete clinical remission in two cases; in three patients there was a partial therapeutic effect.	Medicinal Biomagnetism has the potential to aid in the treatment
Damyanov <i>et al.</i> (2019b)	Application of the Medicinal Biomagnetism technique in conjunction with Insulin Potentiated Therapy (IPT) in patients with advanced metastatic tumors.	Improving the condition of the patient when faced with a diagnosis of tumor phenomena	33 patients undergoing treatment for tumor phenomena	Applied to 33 cancer patients with advanced metastatic tumors, 10 dropped out, 19 out of 23 had previous standard treatment failure. 23 patients completed treatment and follow-up. Of these, 5 patients achieved complete remission and 17 patients achieved stabilization and 1 patient was not informed of the	Biomagnetic therapy with magnetic pairs is an innovative and promising method for the treatment of chronic and oncological diseases.

Authors	Method	Goal	Participants	Result	Conclusion
FRANK, 2017	Applied a single session of the MB technique, lasting 3 to 5 minutes with the magnets remaining as the only tool	Patients with laboratory-documented typhoid fever who have been treated with Biomagnetic Pair Therapy (BPT; medical biomagnetism), a specific application of pairs of magnets for various infectious and other diseases	13 people who tested positive for Salmonella typhi infection detected by the standard Widal test method.	Most participants (10 of 13) retested as negative, and all patients reported clinical symptoms of improvement.	A significant majority of participants demonstrated clearance of their S. typhi after BPT, this technique should be further studied in larger studies for its effectiveness in treating typhoid fever.
SILVA <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Group G1 underwent intervention associated with a therapeutic exercise program and group G2 underwent an exercise program associated with magnetotherapy with MAGNETHERAP equipment	The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of magnetotherapy in the treatment of pain in patients with knee osteoarthritis.	20 volunteers with knee Osteoarthritis	It was observed that the study showed a significant static difference between the variables *p	Magnetotherapy reduces pain and improves the functional capacity of patients with osteoarthritis of the knee.
BROWN <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Applied active 500 Gauss magnetic nets or placebos to abdominal trigger points. used the McGill Pain Questionnaire	It significantly improves intensity and even reduced pain when used continuously for 4 weeks. McGill Pain Questionnaire	32 women of which 19 completed the 4 weeks of treatment. They were in 8 subjects in active treatment and 11 subjects in placebo treatment in a gynecology clinic,	To verify the effectiveness of static magnetic field therapy in the treatment of chronic pelvic pain	SMF therapy significantly improves disability and may reduce pain when active magnets are used continuously for 4 weeks in patients with CPP.

Below, we present the Prostate Cancer Diseases Protocol, prepared by Dr. David Goiz Martínez (Table 1).

Dr. Isaac Goiz mentions that nothing replaces the full screening of BMPs as it is the starting point for any initial investigation. Any protocol is complementary to this screening since it cannot be said that there are no other bioelectrical and/or bioenergetic dysfunctions in other anatomical regions (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008, 2017; MARTÍNEZ, 2017).

Table 1: Sequence of application of the Protocol for the Treatment of Prostate Cancer

Basic Protocol
TOP 10 – Urological
TOP 10 – Oncogenic
TOP 10 – Pathogenic
TOP 10 – Psychoemotional
TOP 10 – Psychiatric
TOP 05 – Detoxification
Deferent duct – Larynx
Coccyx – Coccyx
Prostate – Rectum
Prostate – Prostate
Inguinal Fold (R/L) – Kidney (R/L) (Conflict Zone)

Source: Martínez (2017, page 223).

It is important to note that some of the Basic Protocol BMPs follow a certain form of impaction as presented by Dr. David Goiz Martínez (2017) at the XVI

International Congress of Biomagnetism in October 2017 in Mexico. Next, the BMPs that make up each item described in Table 1 are presented.

The Figures show the anatomical regions and the colors of the magnets that are in contact with the skin, for example, the PBM Thymus – Rectum, the Thymus tracking point is blue (-), therefore, it is this color that will be in contact with the skin and likewise the Recto resonance point will be colored red (+). Conventions used: When writing PBMs, the Tracking Point (-) is followed by the Resonance Point (+). There is still (R) – Right side of the body or region; (L) – Left side of the body or region; (R/L) – Right or left side; (AS) – Against Side.

Figure 2: Basic Protocol BMPs

Legend: 1 – Liver/ Liver; 2 – Liver/Kidney (R); 3 – Kidney (R/L)/ Kidney (R/L); 4 – Spinal Bulb/Lumbar 3/4; 5 – Supraspinous (R/L)/ SupraSpinous (R/L); 6 – Thymus/Rectum; 7 – Hip (R)/ Hip (L); 8 – Cardia/Appendix; 9 – Transverse Colon / Liver; 10 – Thyroid (R/L)/ Thyroid (AS); 11 – Testicle (R/L)/ Testicle (AS); 12 – Lumbar/Kidney (R/L). Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

Figure 3: TOP 10 BMPs – Urologica

Legend: 1 – Kidney (R)/Kidney (L); 2 – Bladder/Bladder; 3 – Thymus/Rectum; 4 – Supraspinous (R)/ supra spinosum (L); 5 – Descending Colon/Descending Colon; 6 – Coccyx (bottom)/Coccyx (higher); 7 – Urethra/Urethra; 8 – Testicle (R)/Testicle (L);

9 – Deferent duct/Larynx; 10 – Spermatic Conduct/Spermatic Conduct. Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

Figure 4: TOP 10 BMPs – Oncogenic

Legend: 1 – Scapula (R)/Scapula (L); 2 – Gluteal (R/L)/Femoral Vein (R/L); 3 – Descending Colon/Quadriceps (R/L); 4 – Suprahepatic/Suprahepatic; 5 – Supraspinous (R)/SupraSpinous (L); 6 – Post Pineal/Bladder; 7 – Descending Colon/Descending Colon; 8 – Iliac Crest/Iliac Crest; 9 – Pleura/Liver; 10 – Bladder/Bladder. Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

Figure 5: TOP 10 BMPs – Pathogenic

Legend: 1 – Gluteus (R/L)/Femoral Vein (R/L); 2 – Descending Colon/Quadriceps (R/L); 3 – Scapula (R)/Scapula (L); 4 – Appendix/Language (R/L); 5 – Pleura/Liver; 6 – Descending Colon/Descending Colon; 7 – Suprahepatic/Suprahepatic; 8 – Stomach/Transverse Colon; 9 – Iliac Crest/Iliac Crest; 10 – Post Pineal/Bladder. Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

Figure 6: TOP 10 BMPs – Psychoemotional

Legend: 1 – Patella (R)/Packcap (L); 2 – Liver/Heart; 3 – Lung (R/L)/Spine Bulb; 4 – Lung (R)/Lung (L); 5 – Heart/Pancreas; 6 – Spleen/Hypothalamus; 7 – Thymus/Testicle; 8 – Stomach/Heart; 9 – Back of the Hand (R)/Back of the Hand (L); 10 – Instep (R)/Instep (L). Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

Figure 7: TOP 10 BMPs – Psychiatric

Legend: 1 – Post Pineal/Cerebral Amygdala; 2 – Temporal (R)/Temporal (R); 3 – Atlas/Uterus; 4 – Spinal Bulb/Heart; 5 – Trachea/Heart; 6 – Cerebral Amygdala/Thymus; 7 – Occipital/Testicle (R/L); 8 – Pineal/Prostate; 9 – Navel/Testicle (R/L); 10 – Corpus Callosum (Anterior)/Corpus Callosum (Posterior). Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

Figure 8: TOP 5 BMPs – Detoxification

Legend: 1 – Liver/Kidney (R); 2 – Liver/Liver; 3 – Kidney (R)/Kidney (L); 4 – Pancreas/Pancreas; 5 – Lung (R)/Lung (L). Source: Martínez (2017 and 2018).

DISCUSSION

Researcher Perez (2022), in her master's thesis in Applied Physics at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, used NIH3T3 murine fibroblast cells in DMEM-F12 cell culture medium. In this experiment, in cell culture greenhouses, different

magnitudes of MEC were applied for 24 hours in order to verify the effects of exposure to external SMF. Possible differences in cell growth and migration similar to wound closure were recognized, correlating with increased mitosis and change in motility pattern of cells in culture. In the end, significant effects of SMF exposure were identified only on cell proliferation and mitosis rate. However, in front of the magnetic field, the cells did not change their migration speed.

The doctoral thesis in Medicine Medical Sciences by the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Medeiros *et al.* (2020), had cells from the SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma lineage in culture as a sample, with the objective of evaluating stimulation in the face of SMF. As a method, a culture plate supported with NeFeB magnets coupled with different intensities and periods was developed. Two articles originated from this research, the first of which is this review entitled “Static Magnetic Stimulation Induces Cell-type Specific Alterations in the Viability of SH-SY5Y Neuroblastoma Cell Line”. The responses evaluated were cell viability, cell death, cell cycle and expression of BDNF protein (Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor). As a result, exposure of SH-SY5Y cells to SMF for 24 hours led to a decrease in cell viability. There was also a decrease in double positive apoptotic cells associated with an increase in the number of necrotic cells. However, the researchers concluded that the effects of SMF on cell viability are cell-type specific, inducing a decrease in cell viability in SH-SY5Y cells. This suggests that SMF can be a potential tool in the treatment of neural tumors and, moreover, they are safe tools in the protocol used (0.3T SMS/24hs).

Damyanov *et al.* (2019a) used the BM technique in conjunction with Insulin Potentiated Therapy (IPT) in patients with cancers and advanced metastatic tumors. As a result, the study demonstrated complete clinical remission in two cases and in three patients there was a partial therapeutic effect. The duration of treatment with IPT in conjunction with BM was shorter and with no toxic adverse effects when compared to conventional treatment.

In a study similar to the previous one, however, adding vitamin C to the treatment protocol, Damyanov *et al.* (2019b) evaluated 33 patients with advanced metastatic tumors. 10 discontinued treatment, 5 achieved complete remission, 17

achieved disease stabilization and the study lacks information on 1 patient. The researchers conclude that BM therapy with SMF is innovative. The lack of research in this area is limiting and has the potential to be a complementary practice to other treatments already used and in an integrative way.

Another empirical research carried out using the BM technique was carried out in a charity clinic in Kenya, a country on the African continent. Researcher Frank, in 2017, applied a single session of the BM technique, lasting 3 to 5 minutes with the magnets remaining as the only tool in the treatment of 13 people who tested positive for *Salmonella typhi* infection, detected by the standard test method Widal. Of the 13 patients who received the BM treatment, 10 of them demonstrably cleared the pathogen *S.typhi* two days later, with negative results on their Widal tests. However, clinically all participants reported moderate and significant improvement regardless of test results (FRANK, 2017).

Researchers from the Potiguar University in the city of Natal-RN developed an experimental research carried out at the Integrated Health Clinic, with the participation of 20 volunteers with osteoarthritis of the knee, distributed as follows: group G1 underwent intervention with the association of program of therapeutic exercises and group G2 submitted to the exercise program associated with magnet therapy with MAGNETHERAP® equipment, (equipment that generates a magnetic field of high intensity and low frequency). The quality of life questionnaire for Osteoarthritis "WOMAC" was used in the evaluation process; the "TUG" test to assess mobility and functional balance and the analogue visual pain scale "VAS". It is interesting to point out that the results obtained were positive in both intervention situations when compared to the control group. The program with physical exercises significantly improves the functional capacity of osteoarthritis patients, as well as magnetotherapy, which favored a rapid reduction of the inflammatory process and inhibition of inflammatory substances (SILVA *et al.*, 2016).

Another study with the objective of verifying the effectiveness of CME therapy in the treatment of chronic pelvic pain was carried out by researchers from Memphis and New York, with 32 women as initial participants, of which 19

completed the 4 weeks of treatment. 8 participants in active treatment and 11 in placebo treatment were followed in a gynecology clinic, 500 Gauss active magnetic nets or placebos were applied in abdominal trigger points. In the evaluation process, the researchers applied the “McGill” questionnaire, which is considered the best instrument and the most used to characterize and discern the affective, sensitive and evaluative components of pain. The results of this research showed that SMF therapy of bipolar active magnetic nets of 500 Gauss intensity significantly improves intensity and even reduced pain when used continuously for 4 weeks (BROWN *et al.*, 2002).

The similarities observed between these selected studies were the relevant conclusions that each one of them presents, since they demonstrated the possibility of obtaining positive and functional benefits through the application of SMF. Regardless of the intensity of gaussian used by the researchers, which corroborates the problem of this present literature review research. Beneficial effects are suggested in view of the exposure of a SMF in the application of the BM technique as a complementary therapy in the treatment of Prostatic Adenocarcinoma.

The BM technique was used by Dr. Goiz Durán for over 33 years and his legacy continues and has spread across the world. The possibilities of positive results in interventions are countless. At the moment, there is no way to measure it because its great proof is in clinical observation, since it is a technique that does not depend on the level of education and can be applied by any person who is qualified, trained by instructors trained in courses within the technique.

As a limiting factor, we point out the lack of case study articles from the sample in the testing and validation of complementary BM therapy as well as the protocol for the treatment of prostatic adenocarcinoma.

The studies validated the apprehension with the scarcity of research in this area, thus, they highlighted the importance of the initiative for new studies and continuity in this segment, seeking greater correspondence of the effectiveness

of the protocol specifically for Prostatic Adenocarcinoma of BM as a complementary therapy.

Given this scenario, it is extremely important that new experiments be carried out with the aim of building and improving future interventions with complementary BM therapy in all spheres of health imbalance, especially in the area of Tumor Phenomena.

The BM technique as a complementary and integrative therapy fits into the humanized primary care model centered on the integrity of the individual for health promotion, according to the assumptions of the ICP in Brazil (2006).

CONCLUSION

Prostate Cancer is responsible for 25% of the male mortality rate and the treatment is a challenge for society and the scientific community.

Although Science has advanced in research on the effects of SMF, there is still a lack of norms and studies that compare the different concepts existing in this subject.

The Legacy of Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán is essential for understanding the bases on which the BM technique is based. There is a need for all this knowledge to be systematized in scientific articles by practitioners and researchers of the technique.

There is the possibility of applying the Protocol for Prostate Cancer, the BM Technique, which can be used simultaneously with allopathic treatments, since it is a complementary therapy, painless, with few side effects, it is not invasive and it is of low cost, being significant the implantation of this technique inside the ICP as a tool with great therapeutic potential to help in the treatment and even remission of tumoral phenomena. Therefore, more people will benefit, contributing to the reduction of pain and suffering for patients, their families and caregivers.

Given this scenario, it is important and urgent that more research be carried out to corroborate the presented protocol.

REFERENCES

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Tumor Phenomena**. 05/02/2022 (Power Point to support the post graduate discipline Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics applied to Health in the South of Brazil, assisted by computer, taught by Instituto Par Magnéti-co) www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br

BOSSA, A.V. **Description of Biomagnetic Pairs**. Par Magnético, 3^a Ed. Cascavel, 2018.

BOSSA, A.V. **Medicinal Biomagnetism Screening Protocol**. Cascavel/PR: Publishing company Independente; Volume 1, Ed. 1 January – 2021. Available in www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Accessed on: June /2022.

BOSSA, A.V. **Advanced Course in Medicinal Biomagnetism**. Cascavel/PR: Publishing company Independente; Volume 1, Ed. 2 Janeiro – 2021. Available in www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Accessed on: June /2022.

BRASIL, Ministry of Health (MH). **National Policy for Integrative and Complementary Practices in the SUS**. Brasília: MH; 2006 Available in: <https://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/pnpic.pdf>. Accessed on: October /2022.

BRASIL, Ministry of Health (MH). **Pan American Health Organization PAHO/WHO**. Brasília: MH; 2021 Available in: <https://www.gov.br/saude/pt-br/aceso-a-informacao/gestao-do-sus/cooperacao-em-saude/parceiros/opas-oms>. Accessed on: October /2022.

BRASIL. Ministry of Health (MH). Secretary of Health Assistance. José Alencar Gomes da Silva National Cancer Institute. **Prostate cancer**. Rio de Janeiro: INCA, 12 mai. 2022. Available in: <<https://www.inca.gov.br/tipos-de-cancer/cancer-de-prostata>>. Accessed on: May 2022.

BRAVO, Barbara Silva, *et al.*, **Prostate Cancer: Literature Review**. Brazilian Journal of Health Review, Curitiba, v.5, n.1, p.567-577 Jan./Feb. 2022. Available in: <https://www.brazilianjournals.com/index.php/BJHR/article/view/42555/pdf>
Accessed on: May 2022.

BROERINGMEYER, R., **Principles of Magnetic Therapy/Biomagnetism**. Health Industries, Inc, 1991.

BROWN, C.S. *et al.*, **Efficacy of Static Magnetic Field Therapy in chronic pelvic pain: a double-blind pilot study**. Vol.187, n° 6, Am J Obstet Gynecol, Dec. 2002.

CARNEIRO, A. A. O.; FERREIRA, A.; MORAES, E. R.; ARAUJO, D. B.; SOSA, M.; BAFFA, O. **Biomagnetism: Instrumental Aspects and Applications**. Brazilian Journal of Physics Teaching. v. 22, n. 3, p. 324-338, 2000.

DAMYANOV, C.; MASLEV, I.; PAVLOV, V.; TODOROV, A. **A new treatment method of Advanced Metastatic Tumors**. Annals of Clinical Case Reports. v. 4, n. 1647, p. 1-6, April, 2019a.

DAMYANOV, C.; MASLEV, I.; PAVLOV, V.; TODOROV, A. **Integrative oncology at the clinician's look chronology for the creation and development of the IPT & BMP Method for treatment of oncological diseases**. Clinics in Oncology. v. 4, n. 1671, p. 1-5, Nov. 2019b.

DAVIS, A.R.; RAWLS, W.C., **Magnetism and its effects on the Life System**, Acres, 2^a ed. USA, abril, 1996.

FRANK, B. L. **Biomagnetic Pair Therapy and typhoid fever: a pilot study**. Medical Acupuncture. v. 29, n. 5, p. 308-312, 2017. Available in: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29067141/>. Accessed on: May 2022.

GABRIOTTI, L.F.B. *et al.*, **Atypical presentation of prostatic adenocarcinoma: case report**. Arq Health Science, 18(4) 166-9 Oct./Dec. 2011. Available in: https://repositorio-racs.famerp.br/racs_ol/vol-18-4/IDZ%205%20-%20out%20dezembro%202011.pdf. Accessed on: May 2022.

GOIZ DURÁN, I. **El Par Biomagnético**. 5. ed. Chapingo, México D. F.: Chapingo Autonomous University, 171 p., 2008a.

GOIZ DURÁN, I. **El Fenómeno Tumoral**. 3. Ed. Texcoco: Impresiones Emmanuel, 2008b.

MARKOV, M.S. **Electromagnetic Fields and Life**, J Electr Electron Syst 3:1 2014. Available in: <https://www.hilarispublisher.com/open-access/electromagnetic-fields-and-life-2332-0796-3-119.pdf>. Accessed on: July 2022.

MARTÍNEZ, D.G. **Biomagnetism Protocols**, BRI Biomagnetism Research Institute, Independent Publication, 2018.

MARTÍNEZ, D.G. **1st level biomagnetic pairs guide**, BRI Biomagnetism Research Institute, Independent Publication, 2017. Available in: <https://docer.com.ar/doc/sen8sc5> . Accessed on: July 2022.

MARTÍNEZ, D.G. **Guia de pares biomagnéticos do 2º nível**, BRI Biomagnetism Research Institute, Publicação Independente, 2017. Available in: https://asmecolpoz.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Guia-Pares-Biomagnetico_Segundo_Nivel.pdf. Accessed on: June 2022.

MARTÍNEZ, D.G. **XVI International Congress of Medical Biomagnetism**. Official Biomagnetism Channel, 2017. Available in: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jH5kvN-Ru9o&t=21s>. Accessed on: July 2022.

MEDEIROS, H.R. *et.al.*, **Static Magnetic Stimulation Induces Cell-type Specific Alterations in the Viability of SH-SY5Y Neuroblastoma Cell Line**, ANTICANCER RESEARCH 40: 5151-5158, 2020. Available in: [Static Magnetic Stimulation Induces Cell-type Specific Alterations in the Viability of SH-SY5Y Neuroblastoma Cell Line – PubMed \(nih.gov\)](#). Accessed on: July 2022.

PAN AMERICAN HEALTH ORGANIZATION (PAHO/WHO), **Complementary and Integrative Traditional Medicines**, 2006. Available in:

<https://www.paho.org/pt/topicos/medicinas-tradicionais-complementares-e-integrativas>. Accessed on: October, 2022.

PEREZ, I,P,D` A, **The effect of exposure to static magnetic fields on Fibroblasts in Culture**, Master's dissertation presented to the Multidisciplinary Graduate Program in Applied Physics, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, 2022. Available at: [Dissertação-de-Mestrado-Física-Aplicada-UFRJ-O-Efeito-da-Exposição-de-Campos-Magnéticos-Estáticos-sobre-Fibroblastos-em-Cultura-Ísis-Perez-2022.pdf](#). Accessed on: May 2022.

RUELA, L.O. *et al.*, **Implementation, access and use of integrative and complementary practices in the Unified Health System: literature review**, Science collective health 24 (11). Nov.2019. Available in: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31664396/>. Accessed on: October, 2022.

BRAZILIAN SOCIETY OF UROLOGY, Urology Portal, **SBU and SBOC unite to report on national prostate cancer prevention and challenges**. Rio de Janeiro – RJ; 2020. Available in: <https://portaldaurlogia.org.br/publico/novembro-azul/sbu-e-sboc-se-unem-para-informar-sobre-prevencao-e-desafios-nacionais-contr-o-cancer-de-prostata/>. Accessed on: May, 2022.

WHITTEMORE, R.: KNAFL, K. **The Integrative review: updated methodology**.J Adv nurs 2005; 52(5):546-553. Available in: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16268861/> Accessed on: October, 2022.

WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION, (WHO). **WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy 2002-2005**, Geneva: WHO; 2002. Available in: <https://pesquisa.bvsalud.org/portal/resource/pt/lis-7042>. Accessed on: October, 2022.

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